

Assessment of the effectiveness of the UAE media during the economic crisis

Applied study on national faculty staff, UAE University

Author's Detail

Dr. Amina Khamis AlDhaheril

And

Dr. Mai A. Alkhajah

Mass Communication Department

UAE University

Introduction

Studying all forms of economic, social, environmental and industrial crises has gained growing importance these days. The media plays a key role in the management of these crises. It gives the receiving public a lot of information and guidelines on how to deal with such crises and their consequences. It also has an impact on the perception of the public as shown by several media studies and theories. Moreover, the media plays an important role in the formation of public opinion in various societies. However, the task of the media becomes more complicated at times of crises and instability in all societies. Therefore, the media should be well prepared to deal with crises in a professional and effective manner.

There is no doubt that the current economic crisis is really one of the most serious problems has struck the world. The global economy has never seen a crisis with this magnitude since the great depression of 1929. All countries in the East and West suffered from this crisis, but with varying degrees based on each country's position in the global economy. It is a well-known fact that Gulf economies are closely linked to the global economy. This is because Gulf Arab states, including the United Arab Emirates, embrace the capitalist system or the free market economy, whereby the private sector provides goods and services to consumers, while the government plays the role of the legislator and the observer. Moreover, the economies of Gulf States depend -to a large extent- on the global economy to sell their oil products. They also invest oil revenues in foreign countries like the United States and Europe. Therefore, the global financial crisis has had great impact on Gulf countries in general, and the United Arab Emirates in particular because they are closely linked to the global economy.

Background on the current financial crisis:

The entire world from the East and the West has been witnessing a wave of economic recession in varying degrees. However, world indicators show that all countries have suffered from this crisis and the consequences began to appear on the global arena in 2008. Meanwhile, experts and analysts believe that the crisis started in an earlier date. They say that the real causes of the crisis emerged in the United States. Economic experts listed some direct and indirect causes of the crisis as follows:

First: The huge cost of the Iraq war, which led to quadrupling spending during the period from 2003-2008. Therefore, the United State became a debtor rather than a creditor country. It is worth noting that US debt is estimated at about 13.9 trillion dollars.

Second: Corruption, fraud and bribery, which led some leading global banks to lose billions of dollars: Examples include Société Générale, which is the second largest bank in France. It incurred losses of about 9.4 billion dollars. Moreover, several cases of embezzlement in Wall Street amounted to around 50 billion US dollars.

Third: The US subprime mortgage crisis: Real estate companies confiscated millions of houses because owners failed to repay loans. Meanwhile, some banks and companies were forced to give up bad debts and stop all attempts to recover them.

All the above causes and others have aggravated the financial crisis and led to confusion in the global markets. Arab countries were not immune from this problem. Gulf countries in particular have suffered a lot from this crisis because they are economically linked to West. This in turn has led to the suspension of many projects and the laying off of large numbers of expatriate workers, let alone the financial losses in foreign investments.

Literature review:

In view of the fact that the consequences of the current financial crisis have started to appear in the global arena since 2008, it was extremely difficult for both researchers to find any studies that covered the way with which Arab, Gulf or UAE media have dealt with the crisis. Therefore, the researchers reviewed the following studies:

First: Arabic studies:

- 1- Mohamed Shouman study (2001) entitled "Problems in the development of crises and disasters media." The objective of the study was to know the origin and development of research on crises and disasters media, and determine the most important problems of crises and disasters communication media. The researchers concluded that crisis media needs

more development; It was not accurate in the publishing information about crisis; the media played an unbalanced role during all stages of crises and disasters.

- 2- El-Sayed Al-Bahnasi study (2002) entitled “The extent of the dependence of the public on Egyptian media during crises.” This descriptive study relied on survey. It used questionnaire on a sample of 400 Egyptian university students. The study concluded that the Egyptian television has been one of the most important means upon which the public relies to obtain the news, followed by the press. The study also indicated that there is a close link between the confidence of the public in the media and its reliance thereon.
- 3- Khaled Salah El-Din study (2004) entitled “Attitudes of the Egyptian elite towards the management by Arabic news channels (Nile News, Al-Jazeera, Al-Arabia) of Arab conflicts and crises. The researcher concluded that Al-Jazeera Channel is the most committed to introducing all dimensions of Arab identity. The study indicated that the elite believe that the three news channels employ the conspiracy theory as a framework for the explanation of Iraq crisis and the separation wall in Palestine.
- 4- Rifat Aref Al-Dab’a study (2007) entitled, “The reliance of the public on the media to gain information about the avian flu. The researcher presented the problem of the study through this key question: To what extent has the public depended on the media to gain information about the outbreak of avian flu in Egypt? The study concluded that there were differences between the respondents regarding the type of newspapers upon which they relied to obtain information about avian flu. The more the dependence on the media as a source of information, the higher the level of knowledge about the avian flu crisis. The more the reliance of on television, the higher the level of information about the crisis.
- 5- Osama Abdel Rahim Ali study (2008) which dealt with how the press covered the economic crises: A case study of the coverage of the bread crisis in 2008 in Al-Ahram, Al-Wafd and Al-Masry Al-Youm. The results of the study showed that the three newspapers dealt differently with the crisis based on the editorial policy of the each newspaper. Al-Wafd and Al-Masry Al-Youm focused on the political framework. They criticized and blamed the government. Meanwhile, Al-Ahram covered the crisis from an economic perspective rather than the other dimensions. It presented several economic proposals to solving the crisis.
- 6- Hanan Ahmed Solieman study (2008) entitled, “The attitudes of the German elite towards the management by foreign news channels of Arab crises. This study has evaluated the media product through measuring the views of the German elite towards the mechanisms employed by news channels in the management of crises and conflicts. The study concluded that foreign news channels were able to provide information about events and crises and introduce deep backgrounds about all subjects. They also played a role in the formation of the German public opinion towards many Arab crises. Moreover, these channels enjoy the key elements of good media performance such as immediate coverage, honesty, objectivity, depth, professionalism and balance. The study also concluded that the five foreign channels (the sample of the study) have introduced news frameworks that are different from those presented in Arab news channels in their management of the Lebanese crisis as an example. The study has also indicated that there were differences amongst the German elite (academics, politicians, and media professionals) in their evaluation of the impact of the five channels.

Second English studies:

- 1- Kim Sung study (2001), entitled, “Comparative study of news reports of the Asian economic crisis”. The researcher analyzed the elite newspapers from five countries, namely, the United States, Indonesia, South Korea, Thailand and Malaysia. The objective of the study was to pinpoint the differences and similarities in their coverage of the crisis. The Study concluded that the newspapers of the United States and Asian countries, which get the support of the World Bank, used the market liberalization frameworks in presenting the news. Moreover, they did not criticize globalization.
- 2- Durham Frank study (2007) entitled, “The Financial Times coverage of the Thai currency crisis”. The objective of the researcher was to see how the economic and financial press frames the role of the state during the crisis. The study showed that the Financial Times newspaper depended heavily on elite sources in covering the crisis and that it has supported the IMF policy of market liberalization.

The above-mentioned studies contributed to deepening our understanding of the role of the media in covering the crises that hit the human society and how to deal with them. These studies have also played an important role in determining the theoretical and methodological structure of this study and in designing the questions and objectives of the study.

Based on the above, this study examines how the UAE media have managed the current economic crisis from the perspective of a number of academics from different specializations. Those academics represent the educated elite in the United Arab Emirates especially as the study was applied on professors of the UAE University.

Purpose of the study:

This study aims to achieve the following purposes:

- 1- Understand the role of UAE media during the economic crisis from the perspective of the educated elite in the UAE.
- 2- Know whether there has been an effective UAE media plan to manage crises through analyzing the UAE media coverage of the global economic crisis and its impact on the local economy from the perspective of the educated elite.
- 3- To what extent the UAE media was prepared to deal with crises.
- 4- Verify the sources of power of the local media in general and during crises in particular.
- 5- The Study aims in general to enrich the UAE library in particular and the Arab library in general with fresh studies in this field.

Research questions:

- 1- How did the UAE media deal with the global economic crisis and its impact on the UAE society?
- 2- What was the nature of information provided by the UAE media to the public opinion regarding the crisis and its impact?
- 3- Did the UAE media provide objective information about the impact of the global crisis on the local UAE economy?
- 4- To what extent did the UAE public have confidence in the local media coverage and literature during the crisis?
- 5- Did the UAE media affect the attitudes and trends of the UAE public opinion, and what was the nature of this impact?
- 6- Was the media discourse unified amongst the various UAE media institutions?

Significance of the study:

The importance of this study lies in the following:

- 1- The important role played by the media in introducing issues of national interest and in managing various crises as well as contributing to finding solutions to several crises and forming attitudes and events.
- 2- The serious impact of the global economic crisis and its consequences on the United Arab Emirates in general and Dubai in particular.
- 3- The need to know the views of the educated elite and their analysis of the role of the UAE media and the introduction of various visions that would contribute to supporting the role of local media.
- 4- The lack of studies about local media and its role in the management of crises in the United Arab Emirates in general and the local median and how to deal with the crisis in particular.

Theoretical framework:

This study relies on the framing theory, which belongs to the model of moderate impact of mass media. It is also similar to the theory of “the agenda setting”. This theory is based on the fact that the media helps individuals to interpret the events that take place in the world around them through the information, analysis of the issues, positions and attitudes of certain persons, which they get from the media. Therefore, they can understand what is happening around them in the human environment. Hence, mass media provides the concerned persons with information and analyses that help them become aware of the issues of their community. However, the role of mass media is not limited to the provision of news content, as it goes beyond this to explain the meaning of that content through specific frameworks. The concept of framing is like a multi-party mass communication process. The frame indicates the aspects and angles through which various issues, events and subjects are covered. Moreover, framing is an analytical method that was developed by a team of psychologists, social scientists in order to interpret the news and the issues and explain them to the public. The framing theory indicates that the media highlights certain issues or problems and explain them in such a way to acquaint the public with their dimensions and explain their causes and try to find solutions thereto.

In this respect, Entman said, “The framing by the media of a certain issue or an event means the intentional selection of some aspects of that issue or the event and highlight them in the news and the use of a specific style to describe the problem, introduce its causes, evaluate its dimensions and propose solutions” (1). Here, the framing theory converges with the agenda setting theory. Both focus on certain issues and highlight them. Meanwhile, the framing theory is interested in the issues that form the main elements of each subject. Therefore, the framing theory constitutes the second level in discussing the agenda setting theory.

Both researchers think that this theory serves the subject of this study, which revolves around the interpretation and evaluation of how the UAE media dealt the current global financial crisis, and the framework it used in introducing the issue. The media framing theory proposes that information gained by the individuals and their approach towards the various events and issues are

formed and influenced by the media coverage of these issues. Therefore, these frameworks used by the news media affect the knowledge, attitudes and behavior of individuals as well as their decisions.

Method and tools of the study:

This study belongs to the descriptive and analytical school because it attempts to describe, analyze and monitor the performance of the UAE media (Print, radio and television) during the recent global financial crisis through the views of the educated elite in the UAE. The study relies on the field survey method. The researchers have prepared and designed the forms, which were circulated to the community of the study including academics and professors working in various colleges of the UAE University.

The community of the study:

The community of the study consists of 144 members of the teaching staff of various faculties and departments of UAE University. See Table (1)

TABLE 1

Place of work	Number	Percentage (%)
Faculty of Science	14	9.722%
Faculty of Humanities	55	38.194%
Faculty of Law	13	9.0277%
Faculty of Economics	7	4.861%
Faculty of Education	13	9.0277%
Faculty of Engineering	17	11.805%
Faculty of IT	1	0.694%
Medicine and medical sciences	19	13.194%
Agriculture	5	3.8194%
Total	144	100%

The study applied the comprehensive listing method. Those academics and professors were selected from the UAE University, which comprises the largest number of the educated elite. Those academics have the necessary experience and specializations to evaluate the UAE media during the global crisis.

The data collection tool:

The researchers designed the survey based on the objectives of the study, with the questions written in such a way as to serve the research. In order to make sure of the truth and credibility of the survey, the researchers put it to test and arbitration. They presented it to a number of media and economics professors at the UAE University for evaluation. It was tested by a small sample of four professors of the Faculty of Economics and the information department at the UAE University.

The duration of the study:

The form was delivered to the respondents by hand and by email during the period from late 2010 to early 2011.

Definitions of some terms mentioned in the study:

- 1- **The current financial crisis:** It means the global financial crisis, which hit the entire world in 2008 and caused a deterioration of the global economic situation and a fall of the global economy.
- 2- **The UAE media:** it means the print media, radio and television of the United Arab Emirates.

Findings

First Theme: The utilized media and exposure:

The following Table (2) shows that local media topped the means used by the public to follow up the news of the economic crisis that hit Dubai at 40%. It was followed by local television channels at 30%. Meanwhile, the electronic newspapers came third with a modest percentage of 5%. Non-UAE Arab media came fourth with a percentage of 2.3%. Other news media like CNN, BBC, Washington Post, Financial Times, New York Times and Wall Street Journal came last at 2%.

This is a natural result because it was a local issue even if it was related to a global crisis. Therefore, local media was more focused and more interested in the economic crisis than Arab and English media. This means that there was more coverage in local media. The fact that local media took the first place in terms of follow up was due to the nature of the reports that presented the news with analyses and opinion. Electronic newspapers came last because the material, which was available on the Internet, was the same as that which was published in the print media with some brevity.

Table (2)

News media	Exposure	%
Local newspapers	73	40%
TV channels	54	30%
UAE radio channels	19	10%
Websites	11	6%
Electronic Newspapers	9	5%
Non-UAE media	9	5%
Arab non-UAE media	4	2%
Other	3	2%
Total	181	100%

As for the extent of the reliance of the respondents on the media to follow up the news of the economic crisis, there were no clear differences between the UAE television channels, which came first at 15%, followed by the UAE press at 14%. The fact that television came first, with slight margin, in this issue is attributable to its spread and its fast coverage of the events. It should be noted here that both media organs are of great importance for the public and for covering the events. We have also found that the UAE press topped the mass media used by respondents to follow the financial crisis. As much as 87 of the respondents indicated that they gave priority to the UAE press followed by television channels. The UAE radio and other media (the Internet) came third.

As for other respondents who relied on other non-UAE media, the researchers found that foreign satellite channels took the first place by 23%, followed by Arab satellite channels by 20.1%. Foreign press took the same percentage. Meanwhile, foreign radio channels, Arab newspapers and magazines took almost similar percentages of 19% for the former and 18.1% for the latter as shown in Table-3. The fact that foreign satellite channels and foreign press took first place is attributable to the view that foreign media is more objective in introducing these issues and is more reliable and credible in analysis.

Table-3

Follow the crisis through non-UAE media	Number	%
Arab satellite channels	29	%20.13

Foreign satellite channels	33	22.916
Foreign radio channels	27	18.75
Arab newspapers and magazines	26	%8.055
Foreign newspapers and magazines	29	%20.138
Total	144	%100

The results of the first theme can be summarized in the following points:

- Local press took first place followed by the local television channels in following up the news.
- There were slight differences in the reliance of the respondents on local television channels and local press. The percentages were very close.
- The foreign satellite channels and the press took precedence over the Arab media in following of news in other media.

Second theme: The Impact of exposure to the media on UAE public opinion trends and knowledge:

Table-4 shows that most respondents gained adequate information *to some extent* by 81.1%. Meanwhile, 26 respondents indicated that they have acquired *adequate* information about the economic crisis by 19%. This means that the respondents gained information that enabled them to form a sufficient idea about the crisis.

Table- 4

Adequacy of information about the crisis	Number	%
Yes	26	%18.055
To some extent	118	%81.944
No	0	%0
Total	144	%100

Most respondents said that the local media have *to some extent* provided them with adequate information about the crisis by 78.5%.

In terms of the comparison of the adequacy of information between the local and foreign media, the latter took precedence at about 42.4% against 2.8% for the former. However, there was slight difference in the adequacy of information (to some extent) between both of them, as foreign and local media recorded 57.7% and 52.8% respectively. This may be attributed to the fact that foreign media was more independent in publishing information than the local media, which adheres to the policies of the government. We can explain this point from the answer to the question regarding whether the local media coverage of the crisis was linked to the directives of the political leadership in the state or not. Most respondents (95.2%) answered by saying that it was so.

The respondents have indicated that there was a strong link between the local coverage of the economic crises and the directives of the local higher leadership by about 99%. This confirms the fact that foreign media was more independent in the coverage of the news. See Table-6

Table-6

The degree of the link between local media and the higher leadership	Number	%
Strong (80-100%)	135	%98.540
Average (50-80%)	2	%1.459
Weak (10-50%)	0	%0
Total	137	%100

Based on these answers, the respondents indicated that they have higher trust in the foreign media than local media. Around 10.5% said that they have high confidence in the foreign media against 0% for the local media. Some 90% said that they have medium trust in foreign media against 53% for the local media. Lack of trust in the foreign media recorded 0% against 47.2% for the local media. (See Table-7)

Table-7

Degree of trust in local media against foreign media	Local media	percentage	Foreign media	percentage
Have high trust (70-100%)	0	%0	15	%10.416
Have medium trust (10-70%)	76	%52.777	129	%89.583
Have no trust (0%)	68	%47.222		%0
Total	144	%100	144	%100

This may ascribed to the fact that the foreign media is known for its professional and deep analysis and its independence in publishing the news. It steers away from political influence, especially when the news concerns other countries. Therefore, the respondents said that the foreign media was to some extent more objective in covering the economic crisis in Dubai by about 99%, compared to 34.1% for the UAE media. See Table-8

Table-8

Degree of objectivity	Local media	percentage	Foreign media	Percentage %
Objective coverage	4	%3	2	%1
Objective coverage to some extent	49	%34	142	%99
Non-objective coverage	91	%63	%0	%0
Total	144	%100	144	%100

As for the extent of attention accorded by the local media to the crisis compared to foreign media, the respondents indicated that foreign media accorded higher interest in the crisis by 78.5% compared 6.3% for the local media. Meanwhile, the UAE media ranked higher in terms of the medium attention by 51% against 22% for the foreign media. This may be attributed to the fact that the local government did not want to amplify the crisis in order to avoid any confusion in the UAE public opinion. Therefore, the local government media followed the same approach.

Regarding the image produced by the local media about the impact of the economic crisis on Dubai compared to the foreign media, it was as follows:

The local media depicted the image that Dubai was a victim of an international conspiracy by 22.2% against 2.4% in the foreign media.

The local media indicated that the crisis had a negative impact on Dubai by 18% compared to 57% in the foreign media.

The local media said Dubai did not deserve what happened to it by 11% compared to 0% in the foreign media.

The local media said Dubai was still strong by 8.2% compared to 1.4% in the foreign media, which also indicated that Dubai made a lot of mistakes that led to this crisis. We note here that there was some contradiction between the local and foreign media in the presentation of the image of Dubai. See Table-13. About 71.3% of respondents thought that there was great contradiction in the coverage of the crisis in the UAE media organs. Meanwhile, some 25.6% of the respondents said that there was limited contradiction. This may attributed to the fact that each emirate has its own independent local media and to the fact that there is a lack of a federal media to represent all the emirates, let alone the absence of coordination between the media at the state level. (See table-9)

Table-9

The degree of contradiction in news reports in the UAE media bout the crisis	Number	%
1- There is great contradiction	102	%71
2- There is limited contradiction	35	% 24
3- There is no contradiction	7	%5
Total	144	%100

Around 45% of respondents said that there was contradiction between TV and the press. This was a large percentage because it was close to half of the respondents. This contradiction centered on the media reports about the crisis in the first place, followed by the statistics then opinion writings in the newspapers.

Third Theme: Opinion of the respondents on the UAE media coverage of the economic crisis:

Concerning the opinion of the respondents on the media coverage of the crisis, they indicated that the local media followed the news of the crisis regularly. However, it did not discuss or elaborate on the impact of the crisis and how to address it. The media also relied on the policy of trying to find justifications and to blame others for the crisis. Moreover, the media coverage lacked the element of integrity of information provided to the audience. It also lacked the any background about the crisis. Moreover, there were no live images of the events. The media did not present an accurate or detailed background about the financial crisis but it explained its causes to the local and global public opinion. Finally, it lacked credibility in the introduction of the crisis.

Most of respondents indicated that the crisis was severe on Dubai. They also expected that it would continue for a period ranging between three to eight years. (See Table-10)

Table-10

Severity of the global financial crisis on Dubai	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
1- Severe crisis	143	%99.305
2- Medium crisis	0	%0
3- Minor crisis	0	%0
4- Cannot determine	1	%0.694
Total	144	%100

Concerning the media plan for the management of this crisis, the majority of the respondents (90.4%) said that there was no such a plan to confront this crisis. In case of the existence of a plan, some respondents said that the national media council and some foreign public relations companies were responsible for this plan. See Table-11

Table-11

The existence of a media plan for crisis	Number of respondents	percentage
1- Don't think there is a plan	4	%2.777
2- Don't know	10	%6.944
3- There is no plan	130	%90.277
Total	144	%100

The respondents have also indicated that communications measures and activities in the local media focused on the statements of the higher leadership and showed solidarity with Abu Dhabi. They also focused on publishing press releases, hired local, Arab and foreign columnists and conducted interviews with writers. See Table-22. Regarding the most effective communications activities, the respondents said that official meetings and interviews with media professionals and economic decision makers were the most effective followed by press campaigns, the organization of events and special occasions then television propaganda campaigns.

When asked about whether there was coordination between the media and the economic decision making authorities, 63.2% of the respondents said that there was such coordination and 27.1% said that they had no idea about the existence of it. Meanwhile, 57.1% of those respondents who acknowledged that there was coordination said it was strong. This may be attributed to the fact that the economic decision makers represent the higher leadership in Dubai and they are related to the media as shown by the first results of this study. The respondents saw that Al-Bayan newspaper was the most responsive to the government in confronting the financial crisis. This is natural as Al-Bayan newspaper is owned by the government and follows its economic policies. It was followed by Dubai TV channels.

Moreover, 61.3% of the respondents stressed the need for transparency in dealing with the crisis, while 39.5% of them indicated that there was a need for prior planning. See Table-12 below.

Table-12

Proposals	Number of respondents	Percentage
1- Need for prior planning to confront crises	90	%39.473
2- Transparency	138	%60.526

3- Avoidance of remedial policies	0	%0
Total	228	%100

Answers to the questions of the study

The two researchers have managed to answer the questions of the study through the results they have reached as follows:

First Question:

How did the UAE media deal with the global economic crisis and its impact on the UAE society?

The local UAE media showed interest in the economic crisis through its coverage and through the provision of adequate information to the UAE public opinion. Around 52.9% of the respondents indicated that the degree of the UAE media interest in the economic crisis was medium compared to the foreign media. Meanwhile, the UAE media played the role of the news carrier, as it followed up the news of the crisis and provided official information to the UAE public.

Second Question:

What was the nature of the information provided to the society regarding the crisis and its impacts?

The respondents were of the view that the UAE media introduced Dubai as a victim of an international conspiracy and that this crisis had negative impact on it, but not that big effect as shown by the foreign media. They also said that Dubai was still economically strong and doing well. The respondents indicated that the UAE media followed up the news of the economic crisis regularly. However, despite the continuous coverage of the crisis, the media did not discuss its consequences or how to confront it. It also followed the policy of finding justifications and blaming others. The media coverage lacked the integrity of information and live images. It did not provide accurate background about the financial crisis, but it explained the causes of the crisis to the local and world public opinion. Moreover, there was a lack of credibility in presenting the crisis. It acted as a carrier of the news and did not discuss the reasons or analyze the economic situation. Therefore, the UAE media dealt superficially with a crisis of such magnitude.

Third question:

Did the UAE media provide objective information about the impact of the global crisis on local economy of the UAE?

On the question of the objectivity of the UAE media, the respondents said that it was less objective than foreign media. Therefore, the trust of the respondents in the foreign media was higher than that in the local media. They also thought that the UAE media was not independent in covering the crisis and was related to the directives of the higher political leadership.

Fourth question:

To what extent did the UAE public have confidence in the local media discourse and reporting during the crisis?

The respondents said that they did not have confidence in the local UAE media. Around 90.8% of them indicated that they have medium confidence in the local media, while the foreign media won the confidence of all.

Fifth Question:

Did the UAE media have an impact on the attitudes of the public? What was the nature of this impact?

The UAE media managed to affect the attitudes of the UAE public opinion in terms of knowledge and behavioral aspects. The UAE media covered the economic crises adequately and continuously as a carrier of the news. It did not play any analytical role. The respondents stressed fact that the media coverage lacked integrity, objectivity, transparency and credibility in introducing the crisis. This affected the attitudes of the public opinion towards the local media as they lost trust in it. Most respondents said that the media was politicized and lacked independence in introducing the crisis. This made them resort to foreign media for credibility, objectivity and transparency, which they lacked in the local media.

Sixth question

Was the media discourse unified in the various UAE media?

The respondents said that the UAE media was not unified because there was great contradiction in its coverage of the crisis. Around 71.3% of the respondents confirmed this contradiction. Meanwhile, 45% indicated that there was contradiction between the print and visual media. Media reports carried a lot of contradiction followed by statistics, then opinion content in the local press.

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